

Energy-Momentum Density's Conservation Law of Electromagnetic Field in Rindler Space-time

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Abstract: We find the energy-momentum density of electromagnetic field by energy-momentum tensor of electromagnetic field in Rindler space-time. We find the energy-momentum density's conservation law of electromagnetic field in Rindler spacetime.

Keywords: The general relativity theory, The Rindler spacetime, Energy-momentum density, Conservation law

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we find the energy-momentum density of electromagnetic field by energy-momentum tensor of electromagnetic field in Rindler space-time. We find the energy-momentum density's conservation law of electromagnetic field in Rindler space-time.

In inertial frame, the energy-momentum tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ of the electromagnetic field is

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4\pi c} (F^{\mu\rho} F^{\nu\rho} - \frac{1}{4} \eta^{\mu\nu} F_{\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma}) \quad (1)$$

In this time, in inertial frame, Faraday tensors $F^{\mu\nu}, F_{\mu\nu}$ are

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & E_x & E_y & E_z \\ -E_x & 0 & B_z & -B_y \\ -E_y & -B_z & 0 & B_x \\ -E_z & B_y & -B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix}, F_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -E_x & -E_y & -E_z \\ E_x & 0 & B_z & -B_y \\ E_y & -B_z & 0 & B_x \\ E_z & B_y & -B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Hence, the energy density ρ_f^0 and the momentum density $\vec{\rho}_f$ of electromagnetic field are

$$T^{00} = \rho_f^0 = \frac{E^2 + B^2}{8\pi c}, \quad T^{0i} = \vec{\rho}_f = \frac{\vec{E} \times \vec{B}}{4\pi c}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3$$

$$|\vec{E}| = E, |\vec{B}| = B \quad (3)$$

In inertial frame, the energy-momentum conservation law of electromagnetic field is by Noether theorem,

$$T^{\mu\nu}_{, \nu} = T^{00}_{, 0} + T^{0i}_{, i}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3$$

$$= \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{E^2 + B^2}{8\pi c} \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(\frac{\vec{E} \times \vec{B}}{4\pi c} \right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

2. ENERGY-MOMENTUM DENSITY'S CONSERVATION ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD IN RINDLER SPACETIME

Rindler space-time is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right) (d\xi^0)^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} [(d\xi^1)^2 + (d\xi^2)^2 + (d\xi^3)^2] = -\frac{1}{c^2} g_{\mu\nu} d\xi^\mu d\xi^\nu \quad (5)$$

In Rindler space-time, the energy-momentum tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ of the electromagnetic field is

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4\pi C} (F^{\mu\rho}F^{\nu\rho} - \frac{1}{4}g^{\mu\nu}F_{\rho\sigma}F^{\rho\sigma}) \tag{6}$$

In this time, in Rindler space-time, Faraday tensor $F_{\xi}^{\mu\nu}$ is[2]

$$F_{\xi}^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & E_{\xi^1} & E_{\xi^2} & E_{\xi^3} \\ -E_{\xi^1} & 0 & (1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^3} & -(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^2} \\ -E_{\xi^2} & -(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^3} & 0 & (1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^1} \\ -E_{\xi^3} & (1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^2} & -(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^1} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{7}$$

In Rindler space-time, Faraday tensor $F_{\xi\mu\nu}$ is[2]

$$F_{\xi\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^1} & -(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^2} & -(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^3} \\ (1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^1} & 0 & B_{\xi^3} & -B_{\xi^2} \\ (1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^2} & -B_{\xi^3} & 0 & B_{\xi^1} \\ (1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^3} & B_{\xi^2} & -B_{\xi^1} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{8}$$

Hence, the energy density $\rho_{\xi f}^0$ and the momentum density $\vec{\rho}_{\xi f}$ of electromagnetic field are in Rindler space-time.

$$T^{00} = \rho_{\xi f}^0 = \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})} \frac{E_{\xi}^2 + B_{\xi}^2}{8\pi C} \tag{9}$$

$$T^{0i} = \vec{\rho}_{\xi f} = \frac{\vec{E}_{\xi} \times \vec{B}_{\xi}}{4\pi C}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \tag{10}$$

$$|\vec{E}_{\xi}| = E_{\xi}, \quad |\vec{B}_{\xi}| = B_{\xi} \tag{11}$$

In Rindler space-time, the energy-momentum conservation law of electromagnetic field is by Noether theorem,

$$\begin{aligned} T^{\mu\nu}{}_{;\nu} &= T^{00}{}_{;0} + T^{0i}{}_{;i} = T^{0\nu}{}_{;\nu}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ &= \frac{\partial T^{0\nu}}{\partial X^{\nu}} + \Gamma^0{}_{\sigma\nu}T^{\sigma\nu} + \Gamma^{\nu}{}_{\sigma\nu}T^{0\sigma} \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

In this time, affine connections are in Rindler space-time

$$\Gamma^{100} = -(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2}\xi^1)\frac{a_0}{c^2}, \quad \Gamma^{010} = \Gamma^{001} = \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0\xi^1}{c^2})} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \tag{13}$$

Hence, in Rindler space-time, the energy-momentum conservation law of electromagnetic field is

$$\begin{aligned} T^{\mu\nu}{}_{;\nu} &= T^{00}{}_{;0} + T^{0i}{}_{;i} = T^{0\nu}{}_{;\nu} \\ &= \frac{\partial T^{0\nu}}{\partial X^{\nu}} + \Gamma^0{}_{\sigma\nu}T^{\sigma\nu} + \Gamma^{\nu}{}_{\sigma\nu}T^{0\sigma} \\ &= \frac{\partial T^{0\nu}}{\partial X^{\nu}} + 3\Gamma^{001}T^{01} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0} (\frac{E_\xi^2 + B_\xi^2}{8\pi c}) + \vec{\nabla}_\xi \cdot (\frac{\vec{E}_\xi \times \vec{B}_\xi}{4\pi c}) + 3 \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{4\pi c} (E_{\xi^3} B_{\xi^2} - E_{\xi^2} B_{\xi^3}) = 0$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_\xi = (\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3})$$

$$|\vec{E}_\xi| = E_\xi, |\vec{B}_\xi| = B_\xi \tag{14}$$

3. CONCLUSION

We find the energy-momentum density's conservation law of electromagnetic field in Rindler space-time.

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